

1 **Significance of climate indices to benthic conditions across the northern North Atlantic**
2 **and adjacent shelf seas**

3
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7
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10 Circulation (AMOC), North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation
11 (AMO), Subpolar Gyre Index

12
13 **Abstract**

14 The northern North Atlantic Ocean and its adjacent shelf seas, are influenced by several
15 large-scale physical processes which can be described by various climate indices. Although
16 the signal of these indices on the upper ocean has been investigated, the potential effects on
17 vulnerable benthic ecosystems remains unknown. In this study, we examine the relationship
18 between pertinent climate indices and bottom conditions across the northern North Atlantic
19 region for the first time. Changes are assessed using a composite approach over a 50 year
20 period. We use an objectively-analysed observational dataset to investigate changes in bottom
21 salinity and potential temperature, and output from a high-resolution ocean model to examine
22 changes in bottom kinetic energy. Statistically significant, and spatially coherent, changes in
23 bottom potential temperature and salinity are seen for the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO),
24 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation
25 (AMO) and Subpolar Gyre (SPG); with statistically significant changes in bottom kinetic
26 energy seen in the subpolar boundary currents for the NAO and AMOC. As the climate
27 indices have multi-annual timescales, changes in bottom conditions may persist for several
28 years exposing sessile benthic ecosystems to sustained changes. Variations in baseline
29 conditions will also alter the likelihood of extreme events such as marine heatwaves, and will
30 modify any longer-term trends. A thorough understanding of natural variability and its effect
31 on benthic conditions is thus essential for the evaluation of future scenarios and management
32 frameworks.

33 **1. Introduction**

34 The northern North Atlantic region contains a number of deep-sea ecosystems including cold
35 water corals, sponges, and those in hydrothermal fields, with some being classified as
36 Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). These ecosystems are susceptible to changes in
37 climate (Johnson *et al.*, 2018; Sweetman *et al.*, 2017); however, in order to place future
38 changes in context and evaluate management measures, it is vital to understand natural
39 climate variability. Whilst the signals of various climate indices on upper ocean conditions
40 have been investigated (e.g. Frajka-Williams *et al.*, 2017; Hátún *et al.*, 2005), potential
41 effects on benthic conditions, and deep-sea VMEs, remain unknown. In this paper, we ask
42 whether climate indices are associated with statistically significant, and spatially coherent,
43 changes in bottom conditions across the northern North Atlantic region. To achieve this, we
44 use an objectively-analysed observational dataset (EN4) to investigate changes in bottom
45 salinity and potential temperature, and output from a high-resolution ocean model (Viking20)
46 to examine changes in bottom kinetic energy. We provide a first look at the emergent
47 patterns, and examine and describe their spatial coherency and magnitudes. We make some
48 tentative explanations for the physical basis of some of the significant signals, but are careful
49 not to ascribe causality where we investigate only correlation.

50

51 **2. Climate Indices**

52 The northern North Atlantic region, which we here define as that north of 30° N including its
53 adjoining continental shelves and seas (Figure 1), has several multi-annual large-scale
54 physical processes that influence upper ocean climate and have the potential to effect deep-
55 sea ecosystems. These processes are often described using a number of basin-scale climate
56 ‘indices’; the most common being the: North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the strength of the
57 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), the Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation
58 (AMO), and the strength and extent of the Subpolar Gyre (SPG). Time-series of these indices
59 are shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that although we consider each climate index
60 individually, it is likely that they are not fully independent of one another. For example, the
61 SPG may alter ocean heat content and therefore influence the AMO (Häkkinen *et al.*, 2013).
62 Similarly, atmospheric pressure changes related to the NAO may affect the AMO through
63 changes in upper water properties (Yashayaev and Seidov, 2015) and the SPG (Häkkinen *et*
64 *al.*, 2011). Additionally, model studies suggest a possible link between the AMO and the
65 AMOC on longer time-scales (Buckley and Marshall, 2016; Zhang, 2008), although no
66 relationship has been established in the observational record (Lozier, 2010). Despite these

67 possible inter-dependencies, we follow many previous studies (e.g. Häkkinen *et al.*, 2011;
68 Hurrell, 1995; Tulloch and Marshall, 2012; Yeager, 2015) and consider an index individually.
69 This enables us to interpret our results in the context of other research, and investigate if any
70 indices produce similar patterns of variability.

71

72 **2.1 North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)**

73 The NAO is an atmospheric pressure index that influences the position and strength of
74 westerly winds (e.g. Hurrell, 1995) and has several effects on the North Atlantic ocean. Sea
75 surface temperatures show a tripole pattern; during a positive NAO: cooler temperatures are
76 seen south of our study area in the tropical Atlantic, warmer temperatures are observed in the
77 Gulf Stream region in the western Atlantic south of ~45 °N, and cooler temperatures are seen
78 in the main subpolar region centred about Greenland (e.g. Marshall *et al.*, 2001). A further
79 area of warmer temperatures, during a positive NAO, is observed on the western European
80 Shelf extending to the oceanic regions immediately west of the UK and Norway (Visbeck *et al.*
81 *et al.*, 2013). The NAO also effects the intensity of convection in the Labrador and Nordic Seas,
82 which, along with changes in upper waters, determines the properties of intermediate and
83 deep water masses in those basins (Dickson *et al.*, 1996). A positive NAO is associated with
84 cooler and fresher Labrador Sea Water (e.g. Yashayaev, 2007). This signature is spread
85 through the subpolar gyre along the Labrador Sea Water pathways, although transit times to
86 the eastern basins are in the order of five-ten years (Yashayaev *et al.*, 2007a; Yashayaev *et al.*
87 *et al.*, 2007b). In contrast, deep waters in the Greenland Sea are warmer and more saline during
88 a high NAO (Alekseev *et al.*, 2001; Dickson *et al.*, 1996). Finally, Iceland Scotland Overflow
89 Water has a lower salinity during a high NAO (Sarfanov, 2009) with less vigorous flow
90 (Boessenkool *et al.*, 2007). No relationship between Denmark Strait Overflow Water
91 salinities and the NAO is observed (Sarfanov, 2009).

92

93 **2.2 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)**

94 The AMOC is a measure of the strength of the overturning circulation in the important North
95 Atlantic region. This circulation involves the conversion of less dense upper waters to denser
96 intermediate and deep waters, and comprises a northward flow in the upper water column
97 balanced by a return flow at depth. The patterns in upper ocean properties have
98 predominantly been investigated in models, with temperatures showing a dipole signal:
99 during a strong AMOC, cooler temperatures are observed in the Gulf Stream region, and
100 warmer temperatures in the subpolar North Atlantic (Tulloch and Marshall, 2012; Zhang,

101 2008). In observational datasets, warmer sea surface temperatures in the Gulf Stream region,
102 and cooler sea surface temperatures in the subpolar North Atlantic, have been attributed to a
103 weakening AMOC over the past century (e.g. Caesar *et al.*, 2018). This cooling is most
104 pronounced in the Labrador, Irminger and Iceland Basins.

105

106 **2.3 Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO)**

107 The AMO is a measure of mean sea surface temperature over the entire North Atlantic and
108 exhibits low frequency variability with a periodicity in the order of 65-80 years (Kerr, 2000).
109 A positive index is associated with warmer sea surface temperatures over the region, with the
110 greatest warming observed in the western subpolar gyre (Buckley and Marshall, 2016).
111 During negative phases of the AMO, zonally-averaged sea surface temperature anomalies
112 reveal the cooling is also more pronounced north of around 40° N (Frajka-Williams *et al.*,
113 2017).

114

115 **2.4 Subpolar Gyre (SPG)**

116 The SPG is a measure of both the strength and extent of the subpolar gyre, with the most
117 commonly used index being the first principal component of the sea surface height field (e.g.
118 Häkkinen and Rhines, 2004; Hátún *et al.*, 2005). During a high SPG, the subpolar gyre is
119 stronger and expands eastward (Thierry *et al.*, 2008). Eastern areas of the subpolar North
120 Atlantic are more strongly influenced by cooler and fresher subpolar water masses, with a
121 reduction in the presence of warmer and saltier subtropical and inter-gyre water masses that
122 enter from the southeast. This change is reflected in upper water properties, with lower
123 temperatures and salinities observed in eastern areas during a high SPG (Holliday, 2003;
124 Johnson *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, at intermediate depths, cooler and fresher conditions are also
125 seen during a high SPG due to the increased influence of Labrador Sea Water and reduced
126 influence of warmer and saltier Mediterranean Water (Lozier and Stewart, 2008).

127

128 **3. Data and methods**

129 In this work we use an objectively-analysed observational dataset (EN4) to examine changes
130 in bottom salinity (S_{bot}) and potential temperature (θ_{bot}), and output from a high-resolution,
131 eddy-resolving ocean-only model (Viking20) to investigate changes in bottom kinetic energy
132 (KE_{bot}).

133

134

135 **3.1. EN4 data**

136 EN4 is a global, quality-controlled, objectively-analysed, dataset of observed potential
137 temperature and salinity profiles which has been used extensively (e.g. Chafik *et al.*, 2019;
138 Etourneau *et al.*, 2019; Prieto *et al.*, 2015; Yang *et al.*, 2016; Zunino *et al.*, 2017). It
139 combines data from all types of profiling instruments, including ship-based measurements
140 and ARGO floats, and is available as monthly averages (Good *et al.*, 2013). EN4 has a 1°
141 horizontal resolution meaning that smaller spatial features will not be resolved, and that large
142 property gradients, such as around the boundary of basins, will become smoothed. Although
143 EN4 starts in 1900, we limit our analysis to 1959 onwards (to match with Viking20) but
144 extend the analysis until December 2017 to maximise available data.

145
146 Bottom potential temperature and salinity were defined as values in the deepest depth bin at
147 any location. The vertical grid in EN4 varies non-linearly with water depth, ranging from 10
148 m bins in the upper 100 m, to a maximum of ~300 m below 3000 m. Thus measurements at
149 any location will, at the most, be within 300 m of the sea-bed, with this value reducing as the
150 sea-bed shallows. This vertical resolution is unlikely to greatly impact the representativeness
151 of bottom values when the deep waters are weakly stratified; however, any vertical features
152 smaller than the grid box depth will not be resolved. The EN4 dataset reverts to a 1971-2000
153 climatology in the absence of any observations (Good *et al.*, 2013). Information for each data
154 point (i.e. for each horizontal grid point, and at each depth level) is given in the weighting
155 variable, which ranges from approximately zero to one. A value of zero indicates the absence
156 of any observations for that data point, during that month, and that climatology is used.
157 Conversely, a weighting of approximately one indicates a high influence of observations.
158 Here we use a cut-off weighting value of 0.1, i.e. we do not use data with a weighting < 0.1.
159 This value was chosen to ensure that periods with no observations, where EN4 reverts to a
160 pure climatology, were not included in the analyses, whilst as many observations as possible
161 were incorporated.

162

163 **3.2. Viking20 data**

164 Viking20 is a 1/20th degree, hindcast-forced, ocean-only model, covering the northern North
165 Atlantic area. It is nested within a global ocean / sea-ice model using the Adaptive Grid
166 Refinement Scheme (Debreu *et al.*, 2008). The model was initiated with climatological
167 temperature and salinity values, and was forced with CORE2 atmospheric data (Large and
168 Yaeger, 2009). More details of the model configuration can be found in Böning *et al.* (2016).

169 Viking20 has been used in many studies, including those to investigate: the North Atlantic
170 Current (Breckenfelder *et al.*, 2017), convection in the Labrador Sea (Böning *et al.*, 2016),
171 Denmark Strait Overflow Water (Behrens *et al.*, 2017), the Deep Western Boundary Current
172 (Handmann *et al.*, 2018; Mertens *et al.*, 2014), and seasonal changes in the eastern subpolar
173 North Atlantic (Gary *et al.*, 2018).

174

175 We use Viking20 output as five-day averages from 1959 to 2009 to investigate changes in
176 bottom kinetic energy. Bottom horizontal velocities (u_{bot} , v_{bot}) were extracted from the
177 bottom grid point at a particular location. As for EN4, grid box thickness varies non-linearly
178 with depth; from <10 m in the upper 50 m, to a maximum of ~ 250 m in the deepest points of
179 the model domain. The vertical resolution of Viking20 is not dissimilar to that of EN4, and
180 the same limitations apply. For example, real-world smaller-scale frictional effects, such as
181 benthic boundary layers, will not be resolved in the velocity field. As our goal was to study
182 kinetic energy, rather than velocities, u_{bot} and v_{bot} were first linearly interpolated from their
183 respective grids onto the grid containing θ_{bot} and S_{bot} . Bottom mean kinetic energy was then
184 calculated as the sum of the squares of mean u_{bot} and v_{bot} , with the eddy kinetic energy
185 defined as the sum of the variances of u_{bot} and v_{bot} . As our data are five-day averages,
186 variances represent energy of sub-inertial flows.

187

188 **3.3 Ecosystem case studies**

189 As well as considering spatio-temporal patterns at the basin-scale, we examine temporal
190 changes at fourteen case study sites (Figure 1, Table 1). These sites were chosen to represent
191 a variety of potentially vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems across the northern North Atlantic
192 region as indicated by VME indicator records (Morato *et al.*, 2018). The sites also include a
193 number of existing, or proposed, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), Ecologically or
194 Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs) and VME closures (Johnson *et al.*, 2018). Although
195 four sites have maximum depths below 3500 m (Table 1), there is no site that truly represents
196 the abyssal plains of the North Atlantic south of 50° N. This reflects the current absence of
197 VME indicator records in these areas (Morato *et al.*, 2018). Time-series were constructed for
198 each case study site. In EN4, data within each case study polygon were simply averaged for
199 each monthly time-step. As case studies 4 and 10 did not contain any EN4 grid points; time-
200 series for these sites were instead extracted from the nearest EN4 grid point. In Viking20, the
201 model grid is curvilinear. Thus, grid points were accordingly area weighted when calculating
202 averages for each five-day time-step.

203 3.4. Climate indices

204 We consider the four most commonly used climate indices for the North Atlantic Ocean: the
205 NAO, AMOC, AMO and SPG. The NAO index used is defined as the normalised pressure
206 difference between Gibraltar and southwest Iceland (Jones *et al.*, 1997). Data were
207 downloaded from the Climatic Research Unit (<https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/data/nao/>) and the
208 winter (DJFM) mean calculated. As Viking20 is forced with CORE2 atmospheric data, which
209 will include a signature of the NAO, we use the observational NAO time-series to investigate
210 ocean correlations in both the EN4 and Viking20 datasets.

211

212 For the AMOC, we use the commonly used definition of the maximum in the overturning
213 stream function in density space (e.g. Lozier *et al.*, 2019; Mercier *et al.*, 2015). As this index
214 is calculated from oceanic rather than atmospheric variables, and changes in the model and
215 observational AMOC may not be contemporaneous, we compute two AMOC time-series: one
216 from EN4 and one from Viking20. For the observational dataset we used the method of
217 Mercier *et al.* (2015), but using EN4 data along the OSNAP-EAST section (black line, Figure
218 1.a). Geostrophic velocities perpendicular to the section were calculated from EN4
219 temperature and salinity data and referenced to satellite altimetry data. The Viking20 AMOC
220 time-series was calculated using model velocities perpendicular to the OSNAP-EAST
221 section.

222

223 We use an AMO index downloaded from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric
224 Administration ([https://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/time series/AMO/](https://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/time%20series/AMO/)) as monthly averages.
225 This time-series consists of sea surface temperatures, averaged over 0-70 °N before de-
226 trending using a 10 year running mean (Enfield *et al.*, 2001). The AMO is also an oceanic
227 index, suggesting that again a model and observational time-series is required. Although the
228 construction of an AMO index from Viking20 was considered, it was discounted for two
229 reasons. Firstly, the AMO index is calculated using sea surface temperatures over the entire
230 North Atlantic; however, the Viking20 nested model domain starts at 32° N (Böning *et al.*,
231 2016). This makes the calculation of an AMO index from Viking20 more complex. Secondly,
232 Viking20 is an ocean-only model meaning that feedbacks between the ocean and atmosphere
233 are not fully represented. As previous work suggests there is a requirement for fully-coupled
234 models in order to represent important teleconnections (Ruprich-Robert *et al.*, 2017), we
235 focus on the observational AMO index and therefore do not investigate changes in KE_{bot}
236 using Viking20.

237 The SPG index used is defined as the first principal component of the sea surface height field
238 between 40-65° N and 60° W to 10° E (Berx and Payne, 2017). This was downloaded from
239 <https://data.marine.gov.scot/dataset/sub-polar-gyre-index> as monthly averages. Again, we
240 considered extracting out a model-based SPG time-series from Viking20 to use in
241 conjunction with the observational index. However, the basin-averaged sea surface height
242 field in Viking20 exhibits a drift after the mid-1990s, which would redistribute power among
243 the principal components used to generate the SPG index. As such, we again focus on the
244 observational SPG and interrogate only the EN4 dataset. Although there may be a large-scale
245 drift in the Viking20 sea surface height field, gradients in sea surface height and the overall
246 circulation patterns in the model output compare well to observations (e.g. Breckenfelder *et*
247 *al.*, 2017; Gary *et al.*, 2018).

248

249 **3.5 Composite method**

250 In order to investigate any differences in near-bed conditions associated with each climate
251 index, we use the commonly-used composite method (e.g. Häkkinen *et al.*, 2011; Terray *et*
252 *al.*, 2003; Tulloch and Marshall, 2012). For each climate index, “high years” were defined as
253 those exceeding one standard deviation above the mean, and “low years” as those less than
254 one standard deviation below the mean. Composites for the high and low climate states were
255 calculated by averaging properties from all high and low years respectively. One of the
256 limitations of the composite approach is that it only considers high and low states, and not
257 transitional processes between the two. As the Viking20 AMOC time-series shows a long-
258 term trend and we are interested in multi-annual changes, we de-trended this index before
259 creating the composites. The time-series was de-trended by assuming a linear long-term trend
260 which may not be entirely appropriate for low-frequency oscillations. However, the record is
261 too short to establish any low-frequency variability more accurately, and de-trending enables
262 us to investigate multi-annual changes over a 50 year period. The number of months averaged
263 to create each composite are shown in Table 2.

264

265 The statistical significance of observed changes at the 95 % confidence level were tested
266 using the method detailed in Terray *et al.* (2003), which we briefly describe here. At each
267 grid point (X), we assess whether the values observed during the high years, or the low years,
268 (class j), are significantly different from a combined group made up of high and low years
269 only. The years within one standard deviation from the mean are not included because the

270 composite analysis only compares two groups: high and low years. The mean of class j (\bar{x}_j) is
271 therefore compared to the mean of the combined high and low time-series (\bar{x}), with respect to
272 the standard error (equations 1 and 2).

$$273 \quad U(X) = \text{abs}((\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})/s_j) \quad (1)$$

$$274 \quad s_j = \sqrt{(n - n_j)/(n_j \times (n - 1))} \times s \quad (2)$$

275 where: s is the standard deviation of the combined high and low time-series; and n and n_j the
276 number of data points in the combined time-series and class j respectively.

277

278 This procedure tests whether or not the high and low years were allocated randomly from the
279 combined group. If the high years and low years are allocated randomly, $U(X)$ will approach
280 zero. Hence, the larger $U(X)$, the more diverse the high and low years, and the less likely that
281 the high and low years were randomly selected. It should be noted that $U(X)$ calculated with
282 the high years as class j , is identical to $U(X)$ calculated with the low years as class j . We set
283 the critical value as 1.96, with values of $U(X)$ exceeding this indicating that the two means
284 are statistically significantly different at the 95% confidence level.

285

286 **4. Results: long-term mean state**

287 In order to provide a baseline for interpreting temporal changes, we first present the long-
288 term mean and associated variability as basin-wide maps. Since the variability of shallower
289 waters can be orders of magnitude larger than that of deeper waters, the variability maps are
290 shown on a \log_{10} scale to highlight the changes over the whole domain. We use the
291 objectively-analysed observational dataset (EN4) to investigate changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot}
292 (Figure 3), and output from a high-resolution model (Viking20) to examine changes in KE_{bot}
293 (Figure 4).

294

295 The lowest mean S_{bot} values are seen on the North American Shelf (< 34.0) and in the Baltic
296 Sea (< 10.0), whilst the highest S_{bot} values are seen in the Mediterranean Sea (> 37.0) and on
297 the European Shelf west of the UK and Ireland (35.40-35.55) (Figure 3.a). Relatively high
298 S_{bot} values are also seen over the shallower Rockall-Hatton Plateau (35.0-35.3), over the
299 eastern Greenland-Scotland Ridge (35.0-35.2), and along the Norwegian Coast (35.0-35.2).
300 In contrast, fresher conditions (34.4-34.7) are seen north of the Davis Strait. Bottom salinity
301 in areas deeper than ~ 2000 m is fairly uniform (34.85-35.00), although S_{bot} decreases with
302 water depth, and slightly more saline bottom conditions are observed in eastern parts of the

303 subpolar region. There is little difference between S_{bot} values in the northern North Atlantic
304 and Nordic Seas.

305

306 Variability in S_{bot} is strongly related to water depth (Figure 3.b), with the highest variability
307 on the continental shelves ($\pm 0.1-0.4$), and the lowest variability seen in areas deeper than
308 2000 m ($\pm <0.01$). However, there is also spatial variability within these general descriptions.
309 For example, variability is higher in the southern North Sea compared to the northern North
310 Sea and shelf areas west of the UK and Ireland.

311

312 The highest θ_{bot} values (> 15 °C) are seen on the North American Shelf south of around 40
313 °N and in the Mediterranean Sea (>12 °C) (Figure 3.c). Relatively high values are also seen
314 in the southern North Sea and on the European Shelf west of the UK and Ireland (10-12 °C).
315 The coldest bottom conditions (< 0 °C) are seen in the Nordic Seas and north of the Davis
316 Strait. In contrast, θ_{bot} values in the northern North Atlantic range from 1-3 °C with an east-
317 west split. Warmer θ_{bot} values are seen in areas shallower than approximately 2000 m, such as
318 over the Greenland-Scotland Ridge (3-5 °C), around the boundaries of the subpolar basins (3-
319 5 °C), and over the Rockall-Hatton Plateau (4-7 °C).

320

321 Variability in θ_{bot} is again mainly constrained by water depth (Figure 3.d), with the highest
322 values observed in the southern North Sea ($\pm 2.0-4.0$ °C) and on the North American Shelf (\pm
323 1.5-3.0 °C). In contrast, lower variability is observed in the deep northern North Atlantic and
324 Nordic Seas ($\pm < 0.04$ °C). In the subpolar North Atlantic, higher variability (0.04-0.06 °C) is
325 observed in the Labrador Sea and Irminger Sea compared to the more eastern basins.

326

327 The highest KE_{bot} ($> 10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) (Figure 4.a) is associated with the flow of Denmark
328 Strait Overflow Water in the Irminger Sea, and Iceland Scotland Overflow Water in the
329 Iceland Basin. In addition, high KE_{bot} values ($1-10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) are observed in the cyclonic
330 boundary currents of the subpolar gyre, including around the boundary of the Labrador Sea
331 and in the Deep Western Boundary Current. Energetic conditions ($> 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) are also
332 associated with the European Slope Current along the northern European and Norwegian
333 Shelves. Other areas, such as the deep northern North Atlantic and Nordic Seas, have low
334 KE_{bot} ($<0.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$).

335

336 The highest values of eddy KE_{bot} ($1-2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) (Figure 4.b) are associated with the Deep
337 Western Boundary Current, although this is over a wider spatial area than the higher KE_{bot}
338 signal. High eddy KE_{bot} values ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) are likewise associated with the overflow
339 currents, as well as in the convection areas of the Labrador and Irminger Seas. High eddy
340 KE_{bot} is also seen in the European Slope Current, although this is of lower magnitude than
341 that seen for the deeper currents. Finally, areas of higher eddy KE_{bot} are seen on the
342 continental shelves; including in the southern North Sea, on the North American Shelf south
343 of around 40°N , and on both the East and West Greenland Shelves.

344

345 **5. Results: Spatial variability linked to climate indices**

346 Having described the long-term mean and variability, we now examine changes associated
347 with each climate index in turn using the composite approach detailed in section 3.5. Again,
348 we use the objectively-analysed observational EN4 dataset to investigate changes in S_{bot} and
349 θ_{bot} , and output from the Viking20 model to examine changes in KE_{bot} . For EN4, we only
350 describe changes where a cut-off weighting is exceeded for both the high and low
351 composites; this ensures the exclusion of periods with no observations. Plots comparing the
352 spatial footprint of different cut-off weightings, ranging from 0.05 to 0.25, are shown in
353 Figures S1-S4. For the NAO, the spatial distribution of data for cut-off values ranging from
354 0.1 to 0.25 is almost identical. For the AMOC, AMO, and SPG there are some small
355 differences; for example: in the eastern Nordic Seas and around the Reykjanes Ridge for the
356 AMOC, in the eastern Nordic Seas and Iceland Basin for the AMO, and in the eastern Nordic
357 Seas for the SPG. However, all cut-off weightings retain data: on the continental shelves,
358 around the boundaries of the basins of the subpolar North Atlantic, over the Reykjanes Ridge,
359 over the Greenland-Scotland Ridge, over the Icelandic Plateau, and around the boundaries of
360 the Nordic Seas. We chose a cut-off weighting of 0.1 to retain as many observations as
361 possible, with only areas where this is exceeded for both the high and low composites
362 included. Although there is a level of subjectivity when choosing the EN4 cut-off weighting,
363 as an additional control we carried out statistical testing (as detailed in section 3.5). Only
364 changes between the high and low years that are statistically significant at the 95 %
365 confidence level are discussed. As pure climatology would have no significant correlations,
366 we can be sure that any statistically significant patterns are due to the presence of data.

367

368

369

370 **5.1. North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)**

371 The largest changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot} associated with the NAO are observed on the continental
372 shelf areas (Figure 5). The European and North American Shelves are anti-correlated: when
373 the NAO is high, warmer and more saline bottom conditions are seen in the North Sea but
374 cooler and fresher values are seen around Grand Banks. Whilst bottom conditions in the
375 Grand Banks area are -0.5 to -1.3 °C cooler, and -0.1 to -0.25 fresher, during a high NAO
376 period relative to a low NAO period, the North Sea bottom values are 1.0 - 1.3 °C warmer and
377 0.2 - 1.2 saltier. The area to the west of Norway is also 0.03 - 0.5 °C warmer during high NAO
378 periods compared to low NAO periods, although a corresponding S_{bot} signal is absent.

379

380 When investigating signals away from the continental shelves, there is limited observational
381 data, particularly below 2000 m. Nevertheless, some spatially coherent and statistically
382 significant changes can be seen. In the Mediterranean Sea, warmer and saltier bottom
383 conditions (0 - 0.3 °C and 0 - 0.02) are observed during a high NAO. In contrast, lower S_{bot} and
384 θ_{bot} values (< -0.02 and < -0.2 °C respectively) are seen in the subpolar gyre, for example
385 around the boundaries of the Labrador Sea and Irminger Sea, over the Reykjanes Ridge, and
386 over the Rockall-Hatton Plateau. In particular, less saline bottom conditions (-0.02 to -0.04)
387 are observed in eastern areas extending on to the shelf west of Scotland, and over the
388 Greenland-Scotland Ridge along pathways of the North Atlantic Current and European Shelf
389 Current.

390

391 Viking20 output can be used to evaluate changes in KE_{bot} (Figure 6.a). During a high NAO,
392 bottom currents are enhanced along the eastern boundary of the northern North Atlantic with
393 higher KE_{bot} stretching along the European and Norwegian Shelf break, and into the North
394 Sea. This is likely to indicate a stronger European Slope Current during a high NAO. Higher
395 KE_{bot} is also observed along the Denmark Strait Overflow Water pathways around the
396 western boundary of the Irminger Sea, although lower KE_{bot} values are seen around the
397 northern and western boundaries of the Iceland Basin which is influenced by Iceland
398 Scotland Overflow Water. Finally, lower KE_{bot} is seen on shelf areas to the north and west of
399 the Labrador Sea.

400

401 **5.2. Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)**

402 To investigate changes associated with the AMOC, we start by using the post-1993
403 observational AMOC time-series to examine changes in the EN4 dataset (Figure 7.a-b). The

404 North American, European and Norwegian Shelves all have lower S_{bot} values (-0.1 to -0.5)
405 during high AMOC states. While θ_{bot} values are also lower (-0.4 to -0.8 °C) on northern parts
406 of the North American Shelf and around Grand Banks during a high AMOC, south of around
407 50° N warmer (0.5-2.5 °C) bottom conditions are seen. Additionally, on the European Shelf,
408 statistically significant changes in θ_{bot} (-0.4 to -0.8 °C) are only observed in the northern areas
409 of the North Sea. The lower θ_{bot} values during a high AMOC on the Norwegian Shelf are also
410 less pronounced than the observed freshening. Hence, on the continental shelves, changes in
411 S_{bot} and θ_{bot} associated with the NAO are not simply correlated.

412

413 Moving now to oceanic areas, fresher and in particular cooler conditions are seen in most
414 regions during a high AMOC. The largest changes (up to -0.35 °C and -0.05) are seen around
415 the boundaries of the Labrador Sea, Irminger Sea and Iceland Basin, as well as over the
416 Greenland-Scotland Ridge. Although S_{bot} and θ_{bot} are lower during a high AMOC in the
417 majority of areas, warmer and more saline bottom conditions are also seen. For example, the
418 Rockall Trough and eastern Iceland Basin are up to 0.011 more saline during a high AMOC.
419 More saline conditions are also observed in the eastern Nordic Seas. In contrast, areas of
420 warmer bottom conditions during a high AMOC are patchy. Despite the higher S_{bot} values in
421 the Rockall Trough during a high AMOC, fresher (0 to -0.05) conditions are still observed
422 over the shallower Rockall-Hatton Plateau and on the European Shelf west of the UK.

423

424 As the timing of changes in strength between the observational and modelled AMOC
425 compare extremely well during the contemporaneous period (Figure 2.b, f), we now use the
426 de-trended Viking20 AMOC time-series to interrogate the EN4 dataset (Figure 7.c-d).
427 Applying the Viking20 AMOC time-series to the EN4 data assumes that the relationship
428 between the observed and modelled AMOC persists outside the post-1993 era. However, the
429 advantage is that it increases the amount of observational data used in the construction of the
430 composites (Table 2) therefore increasing the spatial extent of the analysis.

431

432 Many spatial features observed in the composites created using the observed AMOC time-
433 series (Figure 7.a-b), are also seen in those created from the de-trended Viking20 AMOC
434 time-series (Figure 7.c-d). However, the magnitude of changes are often lower in the model
435 AMOC composites. The extended selection period for the ocean observations is particularly
436 noticeable in the relatively data-sparse areas deeper than 2000 m. Changes in bottom

437 conditions are now revealed in the central Labrador and Irminger Seas, and for areas between
438 approximately 40-52 °N, which in the observational AMOC composite had a mean EN4
439 weighting of <0.1 and were therefore greyed out. Bottom conditions in the central Labrador
440 Sea and Irminger Sea are also cooler (< -0.02) and fresher (< -0.2 °C) during a high AMOC.
441 While fresher conditions are seen south of approximately 52 °N, warmer θ_{bot} values are seen
442 in western areas.

443

444 Finally, we use Viking20 and the modelled AMOC time-series to examine changes in KE_{bot} .
445 We present a high minus low map created from the longer de-trended time-series (Figure
446 6.b), which is very similar to the composite compiled from the post-1993 time-series in
447 Viking20 (not shown). Stronger bottom currents are seen around the northern and western
448 boundaries of the subpolar gyre as well as around Grand Banks. KE_{bot} in these areas is 0.5-
449 $1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$ greater during a high AMOC than a low state. Although changes are seen
450 along the European and Norwegian Slopes, these are not statistically significant.

451

452 **5.3. Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO)**

453 As discussed in section 3.4, it is not appropriate to apply the AMO time-series to output from
454 Viking20; thus we examine changes using the EN4 dataset only and do not discuss KE_{bot} .
455 High minus low values for the AMO are positive on the North American, Western European,
456 and Greenland Shelves (Figure 8), with bottom conditions 0.6-1.0 °C warmer and 0.02-0.2
457 more saline during a high AMO. Warmer and saltier conditions are also seen over the
458 shallower Greenland-Scotland Ridge where S_{bot} and θ_{bot} are up to 0.8 °C warmer during a
459 high AMO state relative to a low AMO state, and up to 0.06 more saline. In regions deeper
460 than 2000 m, there is a split between areas north and south of the Greenland-Scotland Ridge.
461 In the deep Nordic Seas, θ_{bot} and S_{bot} are higher during a high AMO. In contrast, cooler and
462 less saline bottom conditions are seen below approximately 2000 m in the northern North
463 Atlantic. The magnitude of the changes in θ_{bot} and S_{bot} in both these regions are $\pm 0-0.02$ and
464 $\pm 0-0.2$ °C respectively. There is insufficient data to assess any changes in areas deeper than
465 2000 m south of around 45-50 °N.

466

467 **5.4. Subpolar Gyre (SPG)**

468 For the SPG, we again only examine changes in the EN4 dataset. Bottom conditions are
469 cooler and fresher during a high SPG for the vast majority of the northern North Atlantic
470 region regardless of bathymetric depth (Figure 9). On the continental shelves, lower S_{bot}

471 values are seen on the North American (-0.15 to -0.50), European (-0.04 to -0.25) and
472 Norwegian Shelves (-0.04 to -0.08). However, decreased θ_{bot} values are observed only on the
473 North American shelf (-0.8 to -1.5 °C) with the absence of a cooling in the North Sea. On the
474 Norwegian Shelf, cooler bottom waters are only seen north of approximately 70° N, even
475 though the change in S_{bot} is widespread. Hence, whilst S_{bot} and θ_{bot} co-vary on the North
476 American Shelf, this relationship does not exist in the North Sea and Norwegian Shelf.
477 Despite the lack of a statistically robust temperature signal in the North Sea, lower θ_{bot} values
478 (-0.2 to -0.8 °C) are still observed on the European Shelf west of Scotland during a high SPG.

479

480 Away from the continental shelves, fresher and cooler conditions are observed in the majority
481 of areas during a high SPG. Changes are particularly pronounced around the boundaries of
482 the Labrador and Irminger Seas, and over the Reykjanes and Greenland-Scotland Ridges. In
483 these areas, bottom conditions are -0.02 to -0.06 fresher during a high SPG, relative to a low
484 SPG, and -0.2 to -0.8 °C colder. Cooler (0 to -0.1 °C) and fresher (0 to -0.01) conditions are
485 also observed in areas of the Labrador and Irminger Seas deeper than 2000 m, although these
486 changes are smaller than those observed at the boundaries. In the eastern subpolar gyre, there
487 are some areas of higher θ_{bot} and S_{bot} . In particular, bottom conditions in the Iceland Basin
488 and Rockall Trough are up to 0.015 more saline during a high SPG than a low SPG. North of
489 the Greenland-Scotland Ridge, the majority of the Nordic Seas show lower θ_{bot} values during
490 a high SPG. However, again there are areas of more saline S_{bot} values, mainly in the eastern
491 portions of the region.

492

493 Finally, we note that the pattern of changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot} seen between the high and low
494 states of the SPG (Figure 9), are very similar to that seen for the AMOC; particularly when
495 considering the post-1993 AMOC time-series (Figure 7.a-b). Although this may reflect a link
496 between the two climate indices, the selection periods for the two indices are very similar
497 (Figure 2.f): the months used to create the high SPG average are almost identical to those
498 used to create the post-1993 high AMOC composite, whilst the input periods for the low
499 composites are sequential to each other. This suggests that a similar signal may be
500 represented for both indices, and thus it is hard to define whether the observed changes are
501 dominated by the SPG, or the AMOC, or indeed whether the two indices act in unison.

502

503

504 **5.5 Comparison between indices**

505 We now examine the spatial dominance of each index by asking a simple question: which
506 climate index is associated with the largest changes at each location? This enables us to
507 examine whether there are spatially coherent patterns, and how these vary both in the
508 horizontal and vertical. As we have investigated more climate indices in EN4, we focus on
509 the changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot} . Again, we only consider changes that are statistically significant
510 at the 95 % confidence level, and where there is a weighting > 0.1 for both the high and low
511 composites. Although the patterns of variability for the AMOC and SPG are very similar, we
512 include both indices separately to see if perhaps there is a spatial difference between the two.
513

514 The dominant climate index pattern is reasonably similar for S_{bot} and θ_{bot} , although they are
515 not identical (Figure 10). Whilst some areas are patchy, there are also some spatially coherent
516 signals and general observations to be made. For example, where there is sufficient data to
517 assess changes below 2000 m, the AMO is associated with the largest changes. This is true
518 both in the Nordic Seas and northern North Atlantic. In contrast, the SPG dominates changes
519 in areas shallower than 2000 m in the western subpolar North Atlantic, whilst the AMOC
520 becomes more important in eastern areas. In the Mediterranean Sea, the NAO is associated
521 with the largest changes, particularly when considering θ_{bot} . Changes on the North American
522 Shelf are dominated by the SPG, whereas the shelf west of the UK is dominated by the AMO.
523 In the North Sea the AMO also dominates changes in θ_{bot} , whilst the AMOC is more
524 important for changes in S_{bot} .

525

526 **6. Results: variability at ecosystem case study sites**

527 We now move on to discussing changes at fourteen case studies (Figure 1, Table 1) chosen to
528 represent various VMEs across the northern North Atlantic region. As these sites cover a
529 number of management measures, such as ESBAs, MPAs and VME closures, and are
530 therefore often considered as a single entity, we show mean conditions averaged across each
531 location. However, we caution that most case studies cover a range of depths (Table 1),
532 which may be subject to different processes and signals, as well as lag periods. As such,
533 changes at a particular depth may be different to the mean conditions for the entire case study
534 site. For example, at Case Study 9 on the Reykjanes Ridge (Figure 1), the SPG is associated
535 with the largest changes in S_{bot} in areas shallower than approximately 2000 m, whilst the
536 largest changes in deeper areas are linked to the AMO (Figure 10). Additionally, if signals at
537 different depths are opposing, changes averaged across the case study as a whole may be

538 muted, despite statistically significant changes in individual depth layers. Similar effects will
539 be produced in spatially heterogeneous areas, for example at case study 14 in the northern
540 North Sea (Figure 1). Here, the AMOC is associated with the largest changes in S_{bot} in
541 southern areas, whilst the largest changes in the northern part of the case study region is
542 associated with the AMO (Figure 10). However, when the S_{bot} changes are averaged over the
543 entire case study region, only the AMO is associated with statistically significant changes.
544 Finally, as changes are often larger at shallower depths, case study averages are likely to be
545 biased towards processes occurring higher in the water column. As such, we advise the reader
546 to consider the results in this section in conjunction with Section 5 and Figures 5-10.

547

548 We again use the EN4 dataset to examine changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot} , and output from Viking20
549 to investigate changes in KE_{bot} although this is only for the NAO and AMOC. Time-series for
550 each case study site are shown in Figures S5-S18, whilst changes between high and low
551 climate states are summarised in Figure 11 and Tables 3 and 4. Again we consider the
552 AMOC and SPG separately, and only describe changes in EN4 where the mean data
553 weighting over the case study as a whole exceeds 0.1 for both the high and low states.

554

555 **Case study 1** is situated on the Norwegian Coast. Here, only changes in θ_{bot} associated with
556 the AMO and SPG are statistically significant at the 95 % confidence level. Both indices
557 show warmer θ_{bot} during high states, with the AMO having the largest change at 0.06 °C. A
558 large positive change in KE_{bot} ($0.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) is also observed between high and low
559 states of the NAO. At **case study 2**, on the western Scottish Slope, all climate indices are
560 associated with significant changes in θ_{bot} . The NAO and AMOC have cooler θ_{bot} values
561 during the high states, whilst the AMO and SPG show warmer θ_{bot} values. The NAO, AMOC
562 and AMO all produce similar magnitude changes. With respect to S_{bot} , only the NAO,
563 AMOC and AMO show statistically significant changes, with all having fresher S_{bot} values
564 during a high state. The largest changes are associated with the AMOC (-0.013) and NAO (-
565 0.011), with the change between high and low states of the AMO half of these values. No
566 statistically significant changes in KE_{bot} are seen.

567

568 **Case study 3** is at Rockall Bank. Here, changes in both θ_{bot} and S_{bot} are statistically
569 significant for all climate indices. Cooler and fresher θ_{bot} and S_{bot} values are observed during
570 high states. The largest change is associated with the AMO for both θ_{bot} (-0.07 °C), and S_{bot} (-
571 0.017). Changes in KE_{bot} though statistically significant are small ($0.01-0.02 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$).

572 **Case study 4**, which has an average depth of 196 m and covers the Mingulay Reef complex
573 to the west of Scotland (Roberts *et al.*, 2009), shows large changes. Statistically significant
574 changes in θ_{bot} are seen for the NAO, AMO and SPG. The NAO has cooler θ_{bot} during a high
575 state, whilst the AMO and SPG exhibit warmer θ_{bot} . All climate indices show significant
576 changes in S_{bot} . The NAO and AMOC have less saline conditions during high states, and the
577 AMO and SPG more saline S_{bot} values. The largest change in both θ_{bot} and S_{bot} is associated
578 with the AMO (0.58 °C and 0.056 respectively). Changes in KE_{bot} between high and low
579 states of the NAO and AMOC are not statistically different at the 95 % confidence level.

580

581 At **case study 5**, on the Porcupine Sea Bight, θ_{bot} shows statistically significant changes for
582 all climate indices. Warmer θ_{bot} values are seen for high states of the NAO and AMOC, with
583 lower θ_{bot} values seen during high states of the AMO and SPG. The largest change in θ_{bot}
584 (0.06 °C) is associated with the AMOC. Only the NAO and AMOC show statistically
585 significant changes in S_{bot} , with the largest change again being associated with the AMOC (-
586 0.011). Changes in KE_{bot} are not significant at the 95 % level for either the NAO or AMOC.

587 **Case study 6** is in the Bay of Biscay. Here, θ_{bot} shows statistically significant changes for all
588 climate indices, with warmer values observed during the high states. The largest change is
589 associated with the AMO (0.08 °C). Only the AMOC does not show a statistically significant
590 change in S_{bot} between high and low states. The NAO and AMO have more saline S_{bot} during
591 high states, with the SPG having lower S_{bot} values. The largest change is associated with the
592 NAO although this is still small at 0.005. KE_{bot} changes, whilst significant, are small (± 0.01
593 $\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$).

594

595 **Case study 7** is located in the Gulf of Cadiz and has a mean depth of 697 m. Here, only the
596 NAO shows statistically significant changes in θ_{bot} and S_{bot} (0.14 °C and 0.034 respectively).
597 In Viking20, the NAO is also associated with weaker KE_{bot} ($-0.22 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) during a high
598 state. **Case study 8** is situated around the Azores and is the deepest site with a mean depth of
599 3064 m. There is insufficient observational data to assess changes here with EN4 weightings
600 < 0.1 for all climate indices. Changes in KE_{bot} , as expected for a deep site away from
601 boundary currents, are negligible.

602

603 At **case study 9**, which is situated on the Reykjanes Ridge, statistically significant changes
604 are observed for all climate indices with both θ_{bot} and S_{bot} . All changes are negative with
605 cooler and fresher bottom conditions during high states. The largest changes are associated

606 with the AMO and AMOC, with both indices having changes of $-0.09\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and -0.012 for θ_{bot}
607 and S_{bot} respectively. Only the AMOC is associated with a small ($0.07 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$), but
608 statistically significant positive change in KE_{bot} between high and low states. **Case study 10**
609 is situated in the Davis Strait. All climate indices show statistically significant changes for
610 θ_{bot} , with cooler conditions during a high state. The largest change is associated with the
611 AMOC ($-0.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), with this being over $0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ greater than changes for the NAO, AMO and
612 SPG. For S_{bot} the NAO, AMOC and SPG all show statistically significant changes in EN4
613 with fresher conditions during a high state. The changes associated with the NAO and
614 AMOC are three to four times that of changes from the SPG, with the largest change
615 associated with the NAO (-0.013). In Viking20, the NAO is associated with less energetic
616 conditions ($-0.59 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) during a high state.

617

618 **Case study 11**, which is situated on the Flemish Cap, shows statistically significant changes
619 with both θ_{bot} and S_{bot} for all climate indices, with cooler and fresher conditions during high
620 states. The largest change in θ_{bot} is associated with the AMOC and AMO, with both indices
621 showing a change of $-0.08\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, the NAO shows only a slightly smaller change of -
622 $0.07\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. All changes in S_{bot} exceed -0.008 , with the largest change of -0.010 again associated
623 with the AMOC and AMO. KE_{bot} shows more energetic conditions ($0.24 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) during
624 a high AMOC. **Case study 12**, covering the USA mid-Atlantic Canyons, has a lack of
625 observational data with EN4 weightings < 0.1 for all climate indices. Additionally, changes
626 in KE_{bot} are not statistically significant.

627

628 At **case study 13**, on the European Slope, the NAO, AMOC and SPG all show statistically
629 significant changes with θ_{bot} , with cooler conditions during high states. The largest change is
630 associated with the AMOC ($-0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), with this being twice the size of changes from the NAO
631 and SPG. With respect to S_{bot} , all climate indices show a statistically significant change in
632 EN4 with fresher conditions during a high state. The largest change in S_{bot} is again associated
633 with the AMOC (-0.019). Both the NAO and AMOC are associated with enhanced KE_{bot} ($>$
634 $0.14 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) during high states. **Case study 14** is in the North Sea and is the shallowest
635 site with a mean depth of 99 m. Only the AMO and SPG show statistically significant
636 changes with both θ_{bot} and S_{bot} . Warmer and more saline bottom conditions are seen during
637 high states, with the largest changes for both parameters associated with the AMO ($0.62\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
638 and 0.046). In Viking20, a statistically significant change in KE_{bot} ($0.17 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) is
639 associated with the NAO.

640 **7. Discussion**

641 In this paper we set out to ask whether there are statistically significant changes in bottom
642 conditions across the northern North Atlantic, and its adjacent shelf seas, associated with four
643 major climate indices, and whether these changes are spatially coherent. The answer to both
644 of these questions is ‘yes’, but what of the physical processes responsible for these changes?
645 This is a more nuanced question. Bottom conditions in the northern North Atlantic region
646 span shallow seas to deep oceans; thus in one map we have contrasting dynamical regimes:
647 from highly seasonal shelf seas, and energetic boundary currents, to quiescent abyssal depths.
648 It is likely that different mechanisms are important at different depths, and lag-times between
649 changes in the index and bottom manifestations will also vary. In this discussion section, we
650 touch on some possible physical processes responsible for observed significant correlations,
651 but anticipate that we only scratch the surface leaving deeper analysis for future work.

652

653 **7.1. North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)**

654 The NAO shows a strong anti-correlation between the eastern and western continental
655 shelves (Figure 5): warmer and more saline bottom conditions are seen in the North Sea
656 during a high NAO, with cooler and fresher conditions in the Grand Banks area. The higher
657 θ_{bot} observed in the North Sea during a high NAO, is likely a representation of the higher sea
658 surface temperatures seen in the same region during a positive NAO (Visbeck *et al.*, 2013)
659 due to the tidally well-mixed water column (e.g. Huthnance, 1991). Bottom kinetic energy is
660 higher during a high NAO along the European and Norwegian Shelf break, and along flow
661 pathways into the North Sea (Figure 6.a). This reduction in the European Slope Current
662 strength in Viking20 during a low NAO, is consistent with evidence of a slowing of the slope
663 current during the 1990’s attributed to changes in both the wind-field and the meridional
664 oceanic density gradient (Marsh *et al.*, 2017). Similar changes are observed in the Norwegian
665 Slope Current with enhanced transport during a high NAO (Skagseth *et al.*, 2004).

666

667 Away from the continental shelves, lower S_{bot} and θ_{bot} values are observed in the subpolar
668 gyre during a high NAO (Figure 5). Convection in the Labrador Sea is enhanced during a
669 high NAO producing cooler and fresher Labrador Sea Water (Yashayaev, 2007). In contrast,
670 convection in the Nordic Seas is reduced during a high NAO resulting in warmer and more
671 saline bottom waters (Alekseev *et al.*, 2001; Dickson *et al.*, 1996). This may explain the
672 cooler and fresher bottom conditions in the Labrador and Irminger Seas. Advection times of
673 Labrador Sea Water to the eastern subpolar regions are in the order of five to ten years

674 (Yashayaev *et al.*, 2007a; Yashayaev *et al.*, 2007b). This suggests that there may be periods
675 where properties of the Labrador Sea Water in the western subpolar North Atlantic may be
676 out of phase to those in eastern areas. However, the temporal spacing between high and low
677 years in the NAO time-series exceeds this, and we see cooler and fresher conditions during a
678 high NAO right across the subpolar latitudes.

679

680 Finally, we see no evidence of the saltier Iceland Scotland Overflow Water during a high
681 NAO observed by Sarafanov (2009), although this is not unexpected for EN4 due to its low
682 horizontal resolution relative to the overflow waters spatial extent. We do, however, see
683 reduced mean KE_{bot} in the Iceland-Scotland Overflow during a high NAO, with coincident
684 increased KE_{bot} in the Denmark Strait Overflow region (Figure 6.a). Less vigorous flow in
685 Iceland-Scotland Overflow Water during a high NAO is consistent with results from a
686 sediment core on the eastern flank of the Reykjanes Ridge (Boessenkool *et al.*, 2007).
687 Additionally, the anti-correlation between the eastern and western overflow branches is
688 consistent with previous work that shows overflow volume transports are correlated with
689 NAO-type changes in sea level pressure and wind stress curl, and that transports between the
690 eastern and western routes can be out of phase (Biaostoch *et al.*, 2003; Bringedal *et al.*, 2018).

691

692 **7.2 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) / Subpolar Gyre (SPG)**

693 As mentioned, the composites produced using the post-1993 AMOC time-series (Figure 7.a-
694 b), and those produced using the SPG time-series (Figure 9) are very similar; probably
695 reflecting the similar time-periods used in the construction of the composites (Figure 2.f). As
696 such, it is difficult to tease out whether the AMOC, or the SPG, is the most dominant index,
697 or indeed whether the two indices act in unison. We therefore discuss both indices together
698 here. Cooler and fresher bottom conditions are seen in the western subpolar North Atlantic
699 during a high AMOC/SPG, with pronounced changes around the boundaries of the Labrador
700 Sea, and over the Reykjanes and Greenland-Scotland Ridges (Figure 7, Figure 9). Lower θ_{bot}
701 and S_{bot} values are also seen over the Rockall-Hatton Plateau and on the continental shelf
702 west of the UK during a high AMOC/SPG, although more saline conditions are seen in the
703 Rockall Trough and Iceland Basin.

704

705 Upper ocean properties show a dipole pattern for the AMOC. During a high AMOC, cooler
706 conditions are seen in the Gulf Stream region, and warmer conditions in the subpolar North
707 Atlantic (Caesar *et al.*, 2018; Tulloch and Marshall, 2012; Zhang, 2008). As such, we may

708 expect to see similar changes in θ_{bot} in shallower areas which are influenced by the upper
709 waters. However, we see no evidence of this; indeed, shallower areas of the subpolar gyre
710 show cooler (and fresher) conditions (Figure 7). This may be because the relationship
711 between upper ocean heat content changes and the AMOC is thought to reflect processes that
712 act on multi-decadal time-scales (Kushnir, 1994; Zhang, 2008), whereas our analysis focusses
713 on multi-annual variability. An alternative possibility is that the SPG dominates upper ocean
714 properties (Figure 9). Upper water properties in the eastern and central subpolar North
715 Atlantic are negatively correlated with the SPG (Hátún *et al.*, 2005; Holliday, 2003; Johnson
716 *et al.*, 2013). Whilst at deeper levels, the SPG has also been shown to effect the eastward
717 extent of Labrador Sea Water (Lozier and Stewart, 2008), as well as the northward limit of
718 Mediterranean Overflow Water (Bozec *et al.*, 2011; Lozier and Stewart, 2008).

719

720 By definition, a high AMOC indicates a stronger overturning circulation with increased
721 northward flow of upper waters and a similar increase in the return flow of deep waters.
722 Additionally, it specifies enhanced conversion of upper waters to denser waters either in the
723 subpolar gyre and/or Nordic Seas. As expected, KE_{bot} is higher in the northern and western
724 boundaries of the subpolar gyre during a high AMOC (Figure 6.b), suggesting more energetic
725 flow in the overflow currents and deep western boundary current. These areas also see a
726 lower θ_{bot} and S_{bot} during a high AMOC, which we speculate may be linked to enhanced flow
727 of cooler and fresher dense waters around the subpolar gyre. Although the KE_{bot} composite
728 was created using the AMOC time-series, we also expect this variable to be effected by the
729 SPG as more energetic flows have been observed during a high state (Häkkinen and Rhines,
730 2004).

731

732 **7.3 Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO)**

733 Spatial changes associated with the AMO are relatively simple (Figure 8). Warmer and more
734 saline bottom conditions are observed: around the boundaries of the northern North Atlantic,
735 on the continental shelves, in the Mediterranean Sea, and in the Nordic Seas during a high
736 state. In contrast, cooler and fresher θ_{bot} and S_{bot} are seen in areas deeper than around 2000 m
737 in the northern North Atlantic. The AMO shows a strong positive correlation with ocean heat
738 content changes in the upper 700 m averaged over 45-70° N (Frajka-Williams *et al.*, 2017).
739 As such, it does not seem surprising that areas influenced by upper waters, such as the
740 boundaries of the subpolar gyre and continental shelves, are warmer during a high AMO
741 state. The high AMO years are seen post-1998, whilst the low AMO years are between 1970

742 and 1994 (Figure 2.d). Therefore, it is possible that our results represent the global increase in
743 ocean heat content over the past half a century (e.g. Levitus *et al.*, 2012), rather than a signal
744 of the AMO. Although we cannot discount this influence, the fact that bottom temperature
745 and salinity co-vary over the vast majority of the northern North Atlantic region (Figure 8),
746 suggests that our composites reflect a process other than just a simple long-term warming.
747 The spatially coherent and statistically significant changes in S_{bot} and θ_{bot} in the deeper
748 northern North Atlantic and Nordic Seas are intriguing. Whilst changes at shallower depth
749 levels and deeper areas are in phase in the Nordic Seas, they appear to be anti-correlated in
750 the northern North Atlantic; that is, during a high AMO the shallower boundaries of the
751 northern North Atlantic are warmer and more saline, whilst the deep interior is cooler and
752 fresher.

753

754 **8. Conclusion**

755 Our results are the first to examine changes in bottom conditions across the northern North
756 Atlantic Ocean, and its adjacent shelf seas, associated with four major climate indices. We
757 show statistically significant and spatially coherent patterns of change between high and low
758 states of the NAO, AMOC, AMO and SPG. Although variations in bottom conditions are
759 relatively small, due to the multi-annual nature of the climate indices any associated change
760 may persist for several years. As such, vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems may be exposed to
761 sustained changes in mean conditions, with this deviation in the baseline also altering the
762 likelihood of extreme events such as marine heat waves. Any changes have the potential to
763 effect sessile deep-sea ecosystems to a greater extent than more mobile pelagic species.
764 Additionally, natural changes will be superimposed on any anthropogenic effects,
765 exacerbating or moderating the impact on possibly stressed ecosystems. Thus, a thorough
766 understanding of natural variability is essential for the evaluation of future scenarios and the
767 implementation of management frameworks. Our work provides a first look at the signature
768 of natural variability on benthic conditions in the northern North Atlantic region; we hope
769 that this stimulates further work both on the physical mechanisms and potential effects on
770 deep-sea ecosystems.

771

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783

784 **Author contributions**

785 MI, SC, CJ and SG contributed to the conception and design of the study. SG extracted the
786 bottom data from Viking20, and MI the bottom data from EN4. CJ carried out the bulk of the
787 analysis and prepared the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to manuscript
788 revision, and read and approved the submitted version.

789

790 **Conflict of interests**

791 None.

792 **References**

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968 *Figure 1. Map of the northern North Atlantic region showing (a) bathymetric features*
 969 *referred to in the text, (b) the 14 case studies chosen to represent a range of Atlantic*
 970 *Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems and management regimes, and (c) a schematic of the*
 971 *circulation. See Table 1 for case study names. Black line in (a) shows the OSNAP-EAST*
 972 *section. Labelled bathymetry: DS: Davis Strait; GB: Grand Banks region; GSR: Greenland-*
 973 *Scotland Ridge; IB: Iceland Basin; IP: Icelandic Plateau; IS: Irminger Sea; LS: Labrador*
 974 *Sea; MAR: Mid-Atlantic Ridge; MS: Mediterranean Sea; NS: North Sea; NoS: Nordic Seas;*
 975 *RR: Reykjanes Ridge; RP: Rockall-Hatton Plateau; RT: Rockall Trough. Contour levels are*
 976 *at 200 m, 2000 m and 3500 m denoting the continental shelves, maximum depth of ARGO*
 977 *floats, and abyssal areas. Labelled currents: DSOW: Denmark Strait Overflow Water;*
 978 *DWBC: Deep Western Boundary Current; ESC: European Slope Current; ISOW: Iceland*
 979 *Scotland Overflow Waters; LSW: Labrador Sea Water; MOW: Mediterranean Overflow*
 980 *Water; NAC: North Atlantic Current.*

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982 *Figure 2. Time-series of climate indices pertinent to the northern North Atlantic region: (a)*
 983 *North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), (b) Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)*
 984 *(black: EN4 time-series, grey: Viking20 time-series post-1993 only), (c) de-trended Atlantic*
 985 *Meridional Overturning Circulation from Viking20, (d) Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation*
 986 *(AMO), and (e) Subpolar Gyre (SPG). All time-series have been smoothed using a five-year*
 987 *Gaussian filter. Solid line shows the mean, and dashed lines \pm standard deviation. (f) shows*
 988 *the high (red) and low (blue) periods for each index that are used in the composite analysis.*

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Figure 3. Maps of mean (a) bottom salinity and (c) potential temperature (°C) between 1959-

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2017 in EN4, and associated standard deviations (b, d). Grey boxes show case study areas.

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To fully resolve variability across bathymetric-depths, (b) and (d) are shown on a log₁₀ scale.

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998 *Figure 4. Maps of (a) mean bottom kinetic energy and (b) associated eddy kinetic energy*
 999 *($\times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) from 1959-2009 in Viking20. Grey boxes show case study areas.*

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1005 *Figure 5. Maps of differences in bottom conditions between high and low states of the North*
1006 *Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) in EN4: (a) bottom salinity changes and (b) bottom potential*
1007 *temperature changes. Transparent grey shading shows areas where the H minus L is not*
1008 *statistically different at the 95 % confidence limit, and solid grey shading areas with an EN4*
1009 *weighting of < 0.1 for either the high or low years.*

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1013 *Figure 6. Maps of differences in bottom kinetic energy in Viking20 between the high and low*

1014 *states of the (a) North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and (b) de-trended 1959-2009 Atlantic*

1015 *Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Transparent grey shading shows areas where*

1016 *the H minus L is not statistically different at the 95 % confidence limit.*

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1019 *Figure 7. Maps of differences in bottom conditions between high and low states of the*
 1020 *Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) in EN4: (a) bottom salinity changes*
 1021 *and (b) bottom potential temperature changes constructed using the EN4 AMOC time-series,*
 1022 *and (c) bottom salinity changes, and (d) bottom potential temperature changes constructed*
 1023 *using the de-trended 1959-2009 Viking20 AMOC time-series. Transparent grey shading*
 1024 *shows areas where the H minus L is not statistically different at the 95 % confidence limit,*
 1025 *and solid grey shading areas with an EN4 weighting of < 0.1 for either the high or low years.*

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1028 *Figure 8. Maps of differences in bottom conditions between high and low states of the*
 1029 *Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO) in EN4: (a) bottom salinity changes and (b) bottom*
 1030 *potential temperature changes. Transparent grey shading shows areas where the H minus L*
 1031 *is not statistically different at the 95 % confidence limit, and solid grey shading areas with an*
 1032 *EN4 weighting of < 0.1 for either the high or low years.*

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1037 *Figure 9. Maps of differences in bottom conditions between high and low states of the*
1038 *Subpolar Gyre (SPG) in EN4: (a) bottom salinity changes and (b) bottom potential*
1039 *temperature changes. Transparent grey shading shows areas where the H minus L is not*
1040 *statistically different at the 95 % confidence limit, and solid grey shading areas with an EN4*
1041 *weighting of < 0.1 for either the high or low years.*

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1045 *Figure 10. Map summarising the climate index associated with the largest change in: (a)*
1046 *bottom salinity, and (b) bottom potential temperature, in EN4. Colours correspond to the*
1047 *dominant climate index, with white areas showing areas where no climate index has*
1048 *significant differences at the 95 % confidence level, and EN4 weightings > 0.1 for both the*
1049 *high or low years.*

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1053 *Figure 11. Summary of changes associated with each climate index at the fourteen case study*

1054 *sites: (a) EN4 bottom salinity changes, (b) EN4 bottom potential temperature changes, and*

1055 *(c) Viking20 bottom kinetic energy changes. Filled circles represent changes significant at the*

1056 *95 % level, whilst unfilled circles show non-significant changes. Changes in EN4 where the*

1057 *data weighting is < 0.1 for either the high or low composite are not shown. The AMOC in (a,*

1058 *b) represents the EN4 time-series, whilst the AMOC in (c) represents the post-1993 time-*

1059 *series from Viking20.*

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Case Studies		Area (x 10³ km²)	Mean depth (m)	Std depth (m)	Min. depth (m)	Max. depth (m)
1	LoVe Observatory	2.2	746	806	1	2298
2	Western Scottish Slope	5.3	596	133	234	952
3	Rockall Bank	301.4	1470	746	21	3026
4	Mingulay Reef	0.1	196	25	148	230
5	Porcupine Sea Bight	218.2	2187	1517	39	4844
6	Bay of Biscay	238.5	2744	2073	1	5026
7	Gulf of Cadiz / Alboran Sea	43.4	697	434	1	1872
8	Azores	954.2	3064	1104	1	5627
9	Reykjanes Ridge	388.1	1927	453	499	3209
10	Davis Strait	8.2	962	537	518	2319
11	Flemish Cap	124.4	1471	1218	128	4664
12	USA Mid-Atlantic Canyons	16.5	750	717	32	2205
13	European Slope	61.2	1243	807	57	3009
14	North Sea	112.0	99	25	40	179

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1068 *Table 1. Description of case study regions chosen to represent a range of Atlantic Vulnerable*
1069 *Marine Ecosystems and management regimes. All statistics exclude areas of land and were*
1070 *calculated using ETOPO2 bathymetry.*

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Climate Index	Relevant figure	N_{high} (months)	N_{low} (months)
NAO	Fig. 5, Fig. 6a	32	60
AMOC (EN4)	Fig. 7a-b	28	16
AMOC (V20)	Fig. 6b, Fig. 7c-d	43	98
AMO	Fig. 8	112	169
SPG	Fig. 9	28	32

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1076 *Table 2. Number of months used to create the high and low composites for each climate*
1077 *index: North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation*
1078 *(AMOC), Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO), and Subpolar Gyre (SPG). For the*
1079 *AMOC two different time-series are used: (1) the EN4 time-series (black, Fig. 2.b), and (2)*
1080 *the 1959-2009 de-trended Viking20 time-series (Fig. 2.c)*

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Case Study	1959-2017 θ_{bot}			1959-2017 S_{bot}			NAO H-L		AMOC H-L		AMO H-L		SPG H-L	
	mean (°C)	min. (°C)	max. (°C)	mean	min.	max.	θ_{bot} (°C)	S_{bot}	θ_{bot} (°C)	S_{bot}	θ_{bot} (°C)	S_{bot}	θ_{bot} (°C)	S_{bot}
1	-1.01	-1.09	-0.92	34.913	34.876	34.954	-	-	-	-	0.06	-	0.04	-
2	-0.81	-1.07	-0.43	34.913	34.848	34.984	-0.09	-0.011	-0.11	-0.013	0.10	-0.005	0.06	-
3	3.62	3.47	3.79	34.969	34.926	35.019	-0.04	-0.010	-0.05	-0.011	-0.07	-0.017	-0.05	-0.012
4	9.54	8.19	11.05	35.375	35.254	35.460	-0.25	-0.022	-	-0.023	0.58	0.056	0.45	0.039
5	3.62	3.48	3.78	35.007	34.983	35.033	-0.03	-0.009	-0.03	-0.011	0.06	-	0.03	-
6	4.36	4.09	4.56	35.063	35.022	35.098	0.06	0.005	0.04	-	0.08	0.003	0.05	-0.003
7	9.40	8.87	10.08	36.000	35.771	36.203	0.14	0.034	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	2.40	2.36	2.49	34.929	34.911	34.946	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	2.90	2.69	3.07	34.952	34.915	34.988	-0.07	-0.006	-0.09	-0.012	-0.09	-0.012	-0.07	-0.009
10	3.22	2.95	3.54	34.912	34.877	35.000	-0.07	-0.013	-0.20	-0.010	-0.05	-	-0.06	-0.003
11	2.49	2.24	2.73	34.911	34.877	34.957	-0.07	-0.009	-0.08	-0.010	-0.08	-0.010	-0.05	-0.008
12	2.96	2.77	3.12	34.955	34.906	34.998	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	3.97	3.74	4.21	34.995	34.921	35.058	-0.05	-0.013	-0.10	-0.019	-	-0.014	-0.05	-0.011
14	7.59	5.89	9.35	35.174	34.838	35.407	-	-	-	-	0.62	0.046	0.49	0.036

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1085 *Table 3. Summary statistics from EN4 for the 14 case studies detailed in Table 1. Columns two and three contain the mean, minimum and*
1086 *maximum for bottom potential temperature and bottom salinity respectively between 1959-2017. All case studies have a mean weighting >0.1*
1087 *except case study 8 where the mean weighting is 0.098. Columns four to seven contain the differences in bottom conditions between high and*
1088 *low states of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation*
1089 *(AMO) and Subpolar Gyre (SPG) respectively. Only differences that are statistically significant at the 95 % confidence level, and where data*
1090 *weightings during both the high and low states are >0.1 are shown. AMOC represents the EN4 time-series.*

Case Study	1959-2009 KE_{bot} ($\times 10^{-2} m^2 s^{-2}$)			NAO H-L KE_{bot} ($\times 10^{-2} m^2 s^{-2}$)	AMOC H-L KE_{bot} ($\times 10^{-2} m^2 s^{-2}$)
	mean	min.	max.		
1	1.44	0.27	5.90	0.96	-
2	1.08	0.41	2.68	-	-
3	0.11	0.04	0.23	0.02	0.01
4	0.48	0.02	3.00	-	-
5	0.06	0.02	0.15	-	-
6	0.05	0.01	0.24	-	0.01
7	2.66	2.09	3.84	-0.22	-
8	0.02	0.01	0.06	-	0.00
9	0.38	0.21	0.61	-	0.07
10	2.09	0.39	3.98	-0.59	-
11	1.51	0.89	2.93	-	0.24
12	0.50	0.07	1.89	-	-
13	0.40	0.06	1.47	0.19	0.14
14	0.28	0.03	1.03	0.17	-

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1092 *Table 4. Summary statistics from Viking20 for the 14 case studies detailed in Table 1.*

1093 *Columns two contain the mean, minimum and maximum for bottom kinetic energy between*

1094 *1959 and 2009. Columns three and four contain the differences in bottom conditions between*

1095 *high and low states of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), and Atlantic Meridional*

1096 *Overturning Circulation (AMOC) respectively. Only differences that are statistically*

1097 *significant at the 95 % confidence level are shown. AMOC represents the Viking20 post-1993*

1098 *time-series.*

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